

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF TURNOVER INTENTION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND EMPLOYEES' JOB PERFORMANCE IN THE HOTEL INDUSTRY

By

Mercy Busayo BELLO, Ph.D. & Yekinni Ojo BELLO, Ph.D.

Federal Polytechnic Auchi, School of Applied Sciences Department of Hospitality / Tourism Management
Technology Edo State, Nigeria.

University of Port Harcourt, Faculty of Management Sciences Department of Hospitality Management and
Tourism Choba, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Corresponding author: bellomercy5@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

This study examined the mediating role of employees' turnover intention on the relationship between job satisfaction, and job performance in the hotel industry in Lagos State, Nigeria. A quantitative research design was used. The population of the study comprised employees of 792 registered hotels in Lagos State. 63 of the 792 registered hotels were selected through systematic random sampling. The employees of the 63 selected hotels put at 1, 624 formed the unit of analysis of the study. Since it is practically impossible for the researchers to sample the entire 1, 624 employees, hence Taro Yamane formula based on proportional allocation was used to determine the sample size of the study put at 330 employees. Partial Least Square (PLS) structural equation modelling was used for the analysis. The study revealed a positive and significant association between job satisfaction and employees' performance. It also found that turnover intention partially and strongly mediates the connection between job satisfaction and employees' performance. These findings may serve as a guide to the formulation, and implementation of policies by human resources, and the management of the hotel industry in Lagos State. The management of hotels in Lagos State may use employees' turnover as a predictor of hotel employee behaviours and then formulate recruitment policies that will help maintain employee satisfaction, and performance thereby helping in employees' retention. The study also confirmed the applicability of Herzberg's Two Factor theories to hotel employees' work behaviour in an emerging economy.

KEYWORDS:

Job Satisfaction, Turnover Intention, Hotel Industry, Employees' Job Performance, Lagos State.

Introduction

The hotel industry is a service-oriented industry that is responsible for the provision of home-away-from-home catering services to tourists. Globally, hotel investment continues to increase steadily, with 2018's totals exceeding US\$68 billion compared to US\$66.4 billion in 2017 (Jones Lang LaSalle IP (JLL), 2019). The industry globally generated US\$ 550 billion in revenue in 2016 and around US\$ 600 billion in 2018 (JCR-VIS Sector Update, 2019). It was reported that the industry hit a record-breaking mark of US\$170 billion in total bookings in 2018 (Deloitte Insights, 2018). In the United States, the hotel industry contributed a total of US\$589 billion to the GDP and US\$167 billion to national taxes (Oxford Economics, 2018). In the United Kingdom, it contributed £57 billion to the UK GDP and accounted for £10 billion of foreign exchange export earnings in 2017 (Oxford Economics for the British Hospitality Association, 2018). In the case of Nigeria, the industry has attracted a significant level of investment put at over US\$3 billion in 2017 (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2017). The indices highlighted above show that the hotel industry is now a mature industry with significant positive impacts on the service economics of countries. Despite the positive business outlook of the hotel industry, the employees of the industry continue to face challenges of job satisfaction (Lee et al., 2015; Wistow et al., 2015), hence exhibiting a higher propensity for job stress (Sprig & Jackson, 2006), and irregular wages (McKay et al., 2012). Other challenges to job satisfaction associated with the employees of the lodging industry include unfair promotion opportunities (Evans & Gibb, 2009), an unfriendly working environment (Lee et al., 2015; Wistow et al., 2015), and poor managerial support from their immediate bosses (Gupta et al., 2014; Kang et al., 2014) among others.

It is therefore pertinent to state that as challenges of job satisfaction increase among hotel employees, the problem of employees' turnover intention also increases (Evans & Gibb, 2009; Kalleberg, 2009). It was reported that the global annual employee's turnover rate of the lodging industry is put at 73.8% with 6% of the hotel staff departing every single month (Bureau of Labour Statistics, 2022). According to the National Restaurant Association (2015), the total employee turnover rate in lodging establishments in the United States was 66.3% in 2014. The average employees' turnover rate in Malaysian hotels was 66% per annum (Kalidass & Bahron, 2015). The overall labour turnover of the Australian hotels was 48.64%, hence, reflecting a managerial staff turnover intention rate of 39.19% and an operational staff turnover intention rate of 50.74% (Akgunduz & Sanli, 2017). However, a statistical report on the extent employee leaves the lodging industry in Nigeria is not in view due to poor data. Nevertheless, symptoms of adverse effects of workers turnover intention rate in the lodging industry in Nigeria include the exorbitant cost of staff recruitment and training, the offering of poor hospitality services, reduction in employee morale, negative and psychological consequences on employees, and, loss of diverse financial and intellectual resources and assets among others. Ashley et al. (2017) argued that reducing employees' turnover tendency is the most important element needed for positive overall hotel performance. This view draws from an understanding that employees are, for the most part, indispensable resources needed by every hotel organisation to achieve high performance (Rana & Singh, 2016a). Gibson (2012) argued that the total performance of a hotel organization is determined by aggregating individual employees' efficiency, effectiveness, and, quality, hence, a tripartite construct. The problem essentially is that hotels in Nigeria exhibit poor employee performance, hence, an increasing level of customer complaints, a decline in occupancy rates, and low profits. The theoretical rationale behind this study is that studies that examined the mediating effect of employees' turnover intention on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in hotels in emerging economies like Nigeria have not been reported. The current study aims to validate the mediating effect of employees' turnover intention on the association between employees' satisfaction and job performance in the lodging industry in Lagos State.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundation

Affect Theory: The Two-Factor theory is adopted for this study. The theory was developed and first used in the domain of organisational behaviour to determine what people want from their jobs (Robbins & Judge, 2009). The theory advances that hygiene and motivational dynamics are responsible for job satisfaction or dissatisfaction, thus impacting employees' turnover intention and performance (Robbins, 2001). This denotes that the theory disjointed job elements that impact employees' satisfaction, turnover, and, performance into two, hence "hygiene" and "motivation" factors. Hygiene factors in this case explain those factors meant to keep employees from dissatisfaction (Robbins et al., 2003). This includes a payment system, bonus system, and other prerequisites. On the other hand, the theory identified job stress (i.e., flexible work schedules, prospect for promotion, employees' empowerment, and, recognition as motivators or intrinsic factors that influenced employees' job satisfaction, turnover, and, job performance (Robbins et al., 2003). Other well-thought-out intrinsic factors that have a direct relationship with job satisfaction, employees' turnover intention, and, job performance highlighted in the theory include work atmosphere, supervisory practices, policies of an organisation, relationships with other workers, and employees' independence (Robbins et al., 2003). As it applies to this study, the theory posits that employees of the hotel industry in emerging countries and particularly in Lagos State, Nigeria would be highly satisfied with their jobs; thus, they will be retaining to experience high performance if hygiene factors and motivators such as job stress, payment system, work environment, promotion opportunities, and supervisor's support are integrated into the management of the hotel industry in the state. Given the applicability of the Two-Factor theory to this study, it was adopted by the researchers.

The Meaning of Turnover Intention

Employees' turnover intention referred to the withdrawal of a worker from the organisation (Bares, 2016; Glissmeyer, 2012; Li, Sawhney & Tortorella, 2019). Hence, employees' determination to quit an organisation. The concept also explained the rate at which employers lose their staff (Chikwe, 2009), thus the movement of personnel across the membership boundary of an organisation. Turnover intention can be defined as an attitudinal (thinking of abandoning), decisional (intention to leave), and behavioural (seeking a new job) process (Khan et al., 2014). Turnover intention is defined as the conscious and deliberate wilfulness to leave the organisation (Meral et al., 2012; Tett & Meyer 1993). It explained the extent to which an employee plans to leave the organisation (Bothma & Roodt 2013; Jacobs & Roodt 2011). The index in the above literature shows that the concept is seen as a voluntary action on the part of the employees to leave a firm at their discretion. This, of course, captures the meaning of the concept in this current study.

The Notion of Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is explained as an employee's attitude towards a job (Cranny et al., 2014; Pushpakumari, 2008). Robbins (2005) defined job satisfaction as a set of emotions that an employee feels about their job. Smith et al. (2007) defined job satisfaction as feelings or affective responses of employees to various facets of their job. The concept can also be defined as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences (Bram et al., 2007). Schermerhorn et al. (2001) defined job satisfaction as the degree to which an individual employee feels positively or negatively influenced by his or her job. Job satisfaction is a touching and passionate response to various facets of one's work (Kreitner & Kinicki 2004). It explained how workers feel about their jobs or a general attitude toward work influenced by the perception of one's job (Singh & Jain, 2013). Jobs in this regard imply the sum of total job facets that constitute workers' experience (Robbins & Judge, 2009). Such an experience needs to be positive for job satisfaction to be achieved.

The Concept of Employees' Performance

Pushpakumari (2008) defined employees' job performance in terms of effort expended on the job by the hotel employee. Efforts in this regard are a form of internal force of a person which makes him or her work willingly. Pradhan and Jena (2016) defined employees' job performance as individuals' work achievement after exerting the required effort on the job. Employees' job performance is therefore defined as the employees' outcome or contributions to the attainment of set goals (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000). Employees' job performance is as well defined as the art to complete a task within defined boundaries (Igbal et al., 2015). Perrin (2016) defined employees' job performance as an individual's outcome based on set standards in terms of accuracy and completeness over a specified period. Platt and Sobotka (2010) defined employees' job performance as quality and quantity achieved by individuals or groups of hotel employees after fulfilling a task. Nmadu (2013) defined employees' job performance as a degree of accomplishment of tasks measured against pre-set standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and, speed. Employees' job performance is associated with the quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence or attendance on the job, morale at work, efficiency, and, the effectiveness of work completed (Mathis et al., 2009). Therefore, the working definition for this study described employees' job performance to connote workers' output rate and the ability to achieve tasks before deadlines, with limited error and complaint rate in line with organisational set goals.

Job Satisfaction and Employees' Job Performance

Tsai et al. (2011) conducted a study on the drivers of hospitality industry employees' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job performance in Taipei City. The findings showed that employees' job satisfaction directly and positively influences organizational performance. Pushpakumari (2008) examined the impact of job satisfaction on job performance in manufacturing and service establishments in Sri Lanka. The study concluded that there is a significant and direct association between job satisfaction and employees' performance in the banking, ceramics, insurance, diary, and paper mail industries in Sri Lanka. Latif et al. (2013) studied the relationship between employees' job satisfaction and organisational performance in five profit and non-profit organisations in the development sector. The result showed that there exists a positive correlation between job satisfaction and organizational performance. Ndule and Ekechukwu (2016) determined the impact of job satisfaction on employees' performance in Nigerian Breweries PLC, Kaduna. The result revealed that a linear relationship exists between job satisfaction and employees' job performance in Nigerian breweries. Dhaifallah et al. (2013) determined the link between job satisfaction and employees' job performance at five-star hotels in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The outcome of the study showed that job satisfaction affects job performance. Ažić (2017) studied the impact of employees' satisfaction on job performance in the lodging industry in Croatia. The study revealed that the job satisfaction of frontline hotel employees correlates with their job performance. However, the fact that the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' job performance has not been tested in the hotel industry in Nigeria made us assume the following hypothesis:

H₁: There is significant relationship between job satisfaction and employees' performance in the hotel industry in Lagos State.

Job Satisfaction and Employees' Turnover Intention

Job satisfaction is an important tool in the domain of organization behaviour. The concepts of job satisfaction and employee turnover are initiated by the antecedents that are in the withdrawal development that forecast voluntary employee turnover. Sangaranand Jeetesh (2015) examined the effects of job satisfaction on employee turnover in the hotel industry in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. The research revealed that job satisfaction influenced employees' turnover intention in the hotel industry in Malaysia. Babushe (2018) examined the determinants of employees' turnover intention in the Bureau of Finance and Economic Development (BoFED) in Ethiopia. The study concluded that job satisfaction predicts employees' turnover intention in BoFED in Ethiopia. Mugove & Mukanzi (2018) studied determinants of employee turnover in selected Kenyan public universities. The results showed

that every unit increase in job satisfaction increases employee turnover in Kenyan public universities. As such from the previous reports, we assume the following hypothesis:

H₂: There is significant relationship between job satisfaction and employees' turnover intention in the hotel industry in Lagos State.

Employees' Turnover Intention and Job Performance

Ferreira and Almeida (2015) investigated the link between employees' turnover and performance in the Brazilian retail sector. The outcome of the study indicates a strong relationship between employee turnover and the sales performance of staff. Rijamampianina (2015) examined the pact of employees' turnover rate and organizational performance of business organisations in South Africa. The results indicate that voluntary employees' turnover rate significantly predicted financial and organizational performance through a cubic function. Ahmed et al. (2016) examined the impact of employee turnover on organizational effectiveness in the telecommunication sector in Pakistan. The outcome of the study showed that there is a significant relationship between employees' turnover and organizational effectiveness. Lee (2018) investigated the correlation between employees' turnover and organizational performance in U.S. federal agencies. The results challenged the accepted belief about the harmful effects of turnover on organizational performance. Thus, confirming that employees' turnover can be beneficial to an organization. Taye and Getnet (2020) examined the impact of employees' turnover on organizational performance at Wada Walabu University, Ethiopia. The result of the study showed that staff turnover causes a reduction in work productivity, and the quality of services rendered. Abubakar and Wainaina (2019) determined the relationship between staff turnover and organizational performance of the selected private hospitals in Kenya. The outcome of the study showed that voluntary and practical turnover favourably correlates with organizational efficiency in the personal medical facility in Kenya. Based on this review, we assume the subsequent hypotheses:

H₃: There is direct relationship between employees' turnover intention and job performance in the hotel industry in Lagos State.

The mediating effect of employees' turnover intention on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance

Al-Ali et al. (2019) examined the mediating effect of job happiness on the relationship between job satisfaction, employee performance, and turnover intention in respect of the oil and gas industry in the United Arab Emirates. The study shows that job happiness plays a full mediating role between job satisfaction and employee performance and turnover intention. Kartika and Purba (2018) examined the mediating effects of affective commitment on the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention of school teachers in an international school in Jakarta, Indonesia. The result of the study shows that affective commitment fully mediated the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. Chen et al. (2019) studied the moderating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between burnout and turnover intention in public primary care institutions in Huangpi, China. The result of the study shows that job satisfaction has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between burnout and turnover intention in public primary care institutions in Huangpi, China. Emely and Susanto (2020) determined the mediating role of job performance on the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention of employees of SMEs in the West Sumatra Province of Indonesia. The study found that job performance fully mediated the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention of employees of SMEs in the West Sumatra Province of Indonesia. Yakoob (2019) investigated the mediating role of job satisfaction on the relationship between leadership style and employees' turnover intention in Al Thiqa private bank in Baghdad. The results of the study show that the effect of leadership style on turnover intention is increased by the mediation of job satisfaction. Based on these studies, we assume the following hypothesis:

H₄: Employees' turnover intention mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in the hotel industry in Lagos State.

Operational Framework

This study determined the mediating effect of employees' turnover on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in hotels in Lagos State. To achieve this objective, the MET-SP model for the hotel industry in Lagos State was proposed as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The MET-SP Conceptual Model.

Methodology

Research design and sampling techniques

Quantitative research design was used in this study, hence a structured questionnaire were administered to obtain information from respondents considered to be representatives of the entire population. The population comprises employees of the 792 registered hotels in the 20 Local Government Areas of Lagos State out of which employees of 63 of the registered hotels were used as the sampling units. The 63 sampled hotels were selected through a systematic random sampling technique; hence the researchers serially numbered all the 792 registered hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State, and automatically picked the first hotel on the list in each of the LGAs while others were picked at an interval of 15. Thus, the employees of the 63 selected hotels put at 1, 624 formed the unit of analysis of the study. Since it is practically impossible for the researchers to sample the entire 1, 624 employees in the 63 selected hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State, hence Taro Yamane formula based on proportional allocation was used to determine the sample size of the study put at 330 employees.

Instrumentation

The instrument used for this study is divided into 4 parts. Part 1 of the questionnaire provides the personal information of each respondent. Part 2 of the questionnaire comprised 5 measures of job satisfaction which include: the Occupational Roles Questionnaire (ORQ) developed by Wu et al. (2010) and the Occupational Stress Indicator (OSI) by Chang and Lu (2009) job stress scales. Items in these scales were modified into 6 items for this study. Job description index, pay satisfaction questionnaire, and job satisfaction survey by Intaraprasong, et al. (2012); Ramirez (2012), Öztürk (2010), and Smith-Randolph (2005) used to measure payment satisfaction were also adopted. These scales were modified into 7 items for the current study. The 10-item scale of the work environment developed by Mohapatra & Srivastava (2003) and Chiang et al. (2005) was modified into a 6-item scale and used for the current study. The promotion opportunity instruments developed by Intaraprasong et al. (2012); Ramirez (2012) and Öztürk (2010) were modified into 4 items scales for this study. Supervisor support scales of Tsai & Tai, 2003; Chiaburu & Takleab, 2005; Tai, 2006; Ismail

et al., 2007; Intaraprasong et al. (2012); Ramirez (2012), and Özturk (2010) were also adapted. The modified instrument consists of 8 items and was used for this study. Part 3 of the questionnaire measured employees' turnover intention, hence a 5-item turnover intention questionnaire developed by Lambert and Hogan (2009) was adapted and used for this study. Part 4 of the questionnaire measured employees' job performance. An 8-item instrument developed by Lee et al. (1999); Sahin (2011), and Motowidloand Van Scotter (1994) was adapted for the current study. Each of the items used for the current study was on a 5-point Likert scale of 1 representing strongly disagree to 5 representing strongly agree.

Data collection and analysis techniques

Convenience sampling technique, a non-probability sampling method that offers no inclusion of criteria was adopted to administer the questionnaires to the respondents. The researchers visited each of the 63 targeted hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State with the aid of research assistance and thus, administered the structured questionnaires to the respondents until the sample size for each of the hotels is met. The data collected were screened in terms of missing values, inferential outliers, normality, and multicollinearity using statistical package for social science (IBM-SPSS) software version 23. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), a multivariate data analysis approach that explores the linear relationships between multiple independent variables and single or multiple dependent variables (Hair et al., 2014) was adopted for the analysis of data collected in this study. The PLS-SEM method enables researchers estimate complex models with many constructs, indicator variables and structural paths without imposing distributional assumptions on the data. Thus, used to examine the measurement, and structural models (Hair et al., 2017b; Shmueli et al., 2016).

Results

Assessment of measurement model

The MET-SP hypothesised model in Figure 1 was evaluated for its construct reliability, including convergent, and discriminants validity using SmartPLS 3.3. The researchers examined the factor loadings of the item variables in the MET-SP hypothesised model. The result of the initial factor loadings reveals that the model does not fit well with the data. Therefore, items whose factor loadings are less than the acceptable threshold of 0.7 as suggested in (Hair et al., 2012; 2014; 20117) were deleted. Given this, 6 items were deleted one item at a time starting from the lowest loading. Observationally, the final MET-SP Measurement Model yielded a better result, hence fits well with the data. Furthermore, the result of the final MET-SP Measurement Model indicators such as Cronbach alpha (α), composite reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), and factor loadings of all items of the study variables in the model yielded a better result as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The Results of the MET-SP Measurement Model

Latent Variables	Items	Loadings	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	(AVE)
Job Satisfaction	SUPER	0.966	0.932	0.967	0.936
	PROMT	0.969			
	JOBP1	0.802			
	JOBP2	0.840			
	JOBP3	0.795			
	JOBP4	0.733			
	JOBP5	0.785			

Job Performance		0.851	0.893	0.627
	EMPT1	0.769		
	EMPT2	0.758		
	EMPT3	0.747		
	EMPT4	0.806		
	EMPT5	0.721		
Turnover Intention		0.820	0.873	0.578

Source: The Researcher’s Computation (2024).

As shown in Table 1, the results of the convergent validity of the final hypothesised MET-SP model show that factor loadings of all the items of the variables in the final MET-SP hypothesised model are statistically significant and exceed the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.7 (Tabachnick&Fidell, 2007). Also, the AVE exceeds the minimum acceptable threshold value of 0.5 (Hair et al., 2006; 2010). Furthermore, the model was evaluated for the internal reliability of the data. Thus, Cronbach Alpha (α), and Composite Reliability (CR) values of all the variables meet the required threshold of 0.7. This implies that all the variables in the TOPEF model have a satisfactory level of internal consistency. Furthermore, the discriminant validity of the final MET-SP hypothesised model was assessed to assure the external consistency of the data. Based on the correlation between the latent variables, the constructs were compared with the square root of AVEs (Hair et al., 2014) as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The Discriminant Validity of the Variables

Constructs	Job Performance	Job Satisfaction	Turnover Intention
Job Performance	0.792		
Job Satisfaction	0.674	0.967	
Turnover Intention	0.602	0.630	0.760

Source: The Researcher’s Computation (2024).

From Table 2, the result shows that the correlations between the constructs are lower than the square root of AVEs along the diagonal. This validates the fulfilment of the discriminant validity requirement.

Assessment of structural model

From a theoretical perspective, the mediation variable tends to explain how significant the role played by employees’ turnover is in linking the effect of job satisfaction to job performance. The bootstrapping method was used, hence the result of the direct relationship between job satisfaction and employees’ job performance as shown in Table 3 is positive and significant.

Table 3: The Direct Hypothesis Testing of Job Satisfaction and Employees' Job Performance

S/n	Hypothesized Path	P-Value	Standard	T Value	Decisions	f-Squared	Effect size
1.	JOBS -> JOBP	0.000	0.003	370.864	Supported	19.434	Large

*P<0.05

Source: The Researcher's Computation (2024).

As shown in Table 3, the result of the analysis shows that the relationship is positive and significant, hence supported. The result of the R-square value shows that job satisfaction tends to influence 95.1% of changes in the dependent variable (i.e., employees' job performance). The remaining 4.9% is due to other factors and residuals. Furthermore, the analysis of the mediation effect (indirect) of employees' turnover intention on the relationship between the independent variable (Job Satisfaction) and the dependent variable (Employees' Job Performance) in respect of the hotels in Lagos State was conducted. The significance of the path coefficients was determined by the beta values of the coefficient of the regression and t-values which were calculated using the bootstrapping method (Hair et al., 2014). The rule of thumb of critical values for a two-tailed test of ≥ 1.96 at a significance level = 5% is considered to be significant (Hair et al., 2014). The result of the analysis is reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Mediation Structural MET-SP Model.

Source: The Researcher's Computation (2024).

Furthermore, for precision, Table 4 shows the summary of the results of the analysis for the indirect relationship between employee turnover on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance as shown below.

Table 4: The Summary of Indirect Hypotheses Testing of Mediating Effect of Employees' Turnover on the Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Employees' Job Performance

S/n	Hypothesized Path	P-Value	Standard	T Value	Decisions	f-Squared	Effect size
1.	JOBS -> JOBP	0.000	0.037	32.309	Supported	3.390	Large
2.	JOBS -> EMPT	0.000	0.043	16.825	Supported	1.061	Large
3.	EMPT -> JOBP	0.001	0.042	3.257	Supported	0.045	Large

*P<0.05

Source: The Researcher's Computation (2024).

Based on Table 4, the hypothesis testing for regression coefficient B_1 (i.e., Job satisfaction and employees' job performance) is positively significant. In addition, the hypothesis testing for regression coefficient B_3 (i.e., Employees' turnover intention and employees' job performance) is positively significant. Again, the hypothesis testing for regression coefficient B_2 (i.e., job satisfaction and employees' turnover intention) is significant. Besides, the value of B_2 (16.83) is smaller than the product of B_3 multiplied by B_2 (54.80). This result implies that the injection of the mediation variable (i.e., employees' turnover intention) into the model validates the existence of partial mediation between the latent construct (i.e., job satisfaction) and the dependent variable (i.e., employees' job performance) in respect of hotels in Lagos State.

Effect size

Furthermore, the strength of the mediation effect was determined using a Variance Accounted For (VAF) (Hair et al., 2014; Tol, 2002). The VAF is obtained by dividing the total effect by the indirect effect and is not constrained to be between 0 and 100. Therefore, the higher the VAF, the stronger the mediation effect (Spector & Jex, 1998; Tol, 2002). Hair et al. (2017) suggested full mediation if $VAF > 80\%$, $20\% \leq VAF \leq 80\%$ indicates partial mediation, and no mediation occurs if $VAF < 20\%$. The result of the analysis shows that the partial mediation has a strong VAF value of 76.7% (i.e., Total effect=0.159; Indirect effect=0.122).

Discussion

This study determined the mediation effect of employees' turnover intention on the relationship between employees' job satisfaction and job performance in the hotel industry in Lagos State. The result of the analysis of the direct relationship between employees' job satisfaction and job performance without the inclusion of the mediator (i.e., employees' turnover intention) showed that the relationship is significant. The outcome of this study supports the report of Pushpakumari (2008) which investigated three groups of employees from twenty private sector organisations, covering five industries in Sri Lanka. The outcome of the study showed that a significant correlation exists between employees' job satisfaction and their performance of employees. In addition, the result of this study agrees with the report of Ndulue and Ekechukwu (2016) which examined the impact of job satisfaction on employees' performance of Nigerian Breweries Plc. Kaduna. The result of the study revealed the existence of a linear relationship between job satisfaction and employees' performance at the brewery. Furthermore, the outcome of this study connects with the report of Mohammed (2016) which examined the relationship between job satisfaction and performance of the non-academic staff of Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria (BASUG). The result of the study showed a significant relationship between job satisfaction and job performance of the non-academic staff of the University.

Additionally, the results of the analysis for the indirect relationship of employees' turnover on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in respect of hotels in Lagos State validate the existence of partial mediation. This finding agrees with other outcomes of various studies. For example, Davar and Ranju Bala (2011), Guest (2004), Opkara (2002), Silla et al. (2005), Schermerhorn et al. (2005), and Spector, (2008) examined the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance, including the mediating effect of turnover intention. They found that the effect of job satisfaction on employees' job performance is fully mediated by employees' turnover intention.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It can be concluded from this study that there is a positive and significant direct correlation between job satisfaction and job performance without the inclusion of the mediator (i.e., employees' turnover intention) of the hotel industry in Lagos State. In addition, it can also be concluded that the indirect relationship between employees' turnover on the link between job satisfaction and job performance validates the existence of strong partial mediation. This implies that one of the potent ways to sustain the positive impact of job satisfaction on employees' performance is for hotel managers to protect the interest, and prevent exploitation of their workers by ensuring strict compliance with the labour act that engenders fair promotional practices, and career development plans. The Nigerian government

should through its supervisory agencies enforce hazard-free working facilities for hotel staff. The owners and management of hotels in Lagos State should avoid discriminatory attitudes towards their staff. The management of hotels in Lagos state should activate performance appraisal schemes to enhance fair promotional practices. They should draw policies that will encourage career development plans of hotel workers. Employees of hotel establishments should be serious with training at work, be self-motivated and always enjoy what they do even if no recognition is given. They should accept the fact that the success of the organisation depends on them. Therefore; they should give their best performance to ensure the continuity of the job to protect their job.

Contribution to Knowledge

To the best of our knowledge, this study, presents the first major study that reported the explanatory power of employees' turnover intention on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance of hotels in Lagos. This study also confirms the applicability of Herzberg's Two Factor theory to study hotel employees' work behaviour in an emerging economy.

References

- Abubakar, A., & Wainaina, L. (2019). Staff turnover and organizational performance of selected private hospitals in Kilifi County, Kenya. *International Journal of Current Aspects*, 3, (6), 309-326.
- Ahmed, A., Sabir, S., Khosa, M., Ahmad, I., & Bilal, M. A. (2016). Impact of employee turnover on organisational effectiveness in the telecommunication sector of Pakistan. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 18, (11), 88-96.
- Akgunduz, Y., & Sanli, S. C. (2017). The effect of employee advocacy and perceived organizational support on job embeddedness and turnover intention in hotels. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 31, 118-125. doi:10.1016/j.jhtm.2016.12.002.
- Al-Ali, W., Ameen, A., Isaac, O., Khalifa, G. S. A., & Shibami, A. H. (2019). The mediating effect of job happiness on the relationship between job satisfaction, employee performance, and turnover intention: A case study on the oil and gas industry in the United Arab Emirates. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 13, (4), 103-116.
- Ashley, R., Jeffrey, S., Oliver, P., & Stephanie, P. G. (2017). *Through guests' eyes: serving up a great restaurant customer experience*. Retrieved August 11, 2018, from Deloitte Consulting LLP: <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/pages/consumer-business/articles/restaurant-customer-experience>
- Ažićb, M. L. (2017). The impact of hotel employee satisfaction on hospitality performance. *Tourism and Hospitality Management*, 23,(1), 105-117.
- Babushe, D. T. (2018). Determinants of employees' turnover intention of Bureau of Finance and Economic Development of Benishangul Gumuz, Ethiopia. *Journal of Resources Development and Management*, 43, (1), 1-7.
- Bares, A. (2016). *Turnover rates by industry*. Retrieved from <http://www.compensationforce.com/2017/04/2016-turnover-rates-by-industry.html>.
- Bothma, F.C., & Roodt, G. (2013). The validation of the turnover intention scale. *South African Journal of Human Resource Management*, 11, (1), 507-519. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm>.
- Bram, C. C., Song, F., & Tapon, F. (2007). Sorting and incentive effects of pay for performance: an experimental investigation. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50: 387-405.
- Bureau of Labour Statistics. (2022). *The employment situation- May 2022*. Retrieved from <https://www.bls.gov/news.release/pdf/empsit.pdf>, on 25th June 2022.
- Chang, K and Lu, L. (2009). The influence of occupation on stressors and work behaviours. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20, (3), 591-605.
- Chen, X., Ran, L., Zhang, Y., Yang, J., Yao, H., Zhu, S., & Tan, X. (2019). Moderating role of job satisfaction on turnover intention, and burnout among workers in primary care institutions: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 19:1526.
- Chiaburu, D.S., & Tekleab, A.G. (2005). Individual and contextual influences on multiple dimension of training effectiveness. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 29, (8), 604-626.

- Chiang, C. F., Back, K. J., & Canter, D. (2005). The impact of employee training on job satisfaction and intention to stay in the hotel industry. *Journal of Humanities Restaurant, Hospitality, and Tourism*, 4, (2), 99 -118.
- Chikwe, A. C. (2009). The impact of employee's turnover: the case of leisure, tourism and hospitality industry *The Consortium Journal*, 14, (1), 43-56.
- Cranny, E.R., Smith, I.I., & Stone., T.U. (2014). Determinants of job satisfaction among police officers. *International Research and Modern Sociology*, 24, (1), 109-116.
- Davar, S. C., & RanjuBala, B. (2011). Relationship between job satisfaction and job performance: a meta-analysis. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 48, (2), 290-305.
- Deloitte Insights. (2018). *Travel and Hospitality Industry Outlook* Retrieved August 10, 2018, from www.deloitte.com/us/travel-hospitality-trends.
- Dhaifallah, O.A. Ebrahim, M., Durrishah, I., Raheleh, E., & Talal Rathan, A. (2013). Job satisfaction and job performance: a case study of five-star hotels in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *World Journal of Social Sciences*, 3, (1), 27 – 37.
- Emely, B., & Susanto, P. (2020). The mediating role of job performance on the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 152, (1), 984-992.
- Evans, J., & Gibb, E. (2009). *Moving from precarious employment to decent work (gurn discussion paper no. 13)*. Retrieved from <http://sindikalizam.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/Evans-John-et-Euan-Gibb-Moving-from-Precarious-Employment-to-Decent-Work-2009>.
- Ferreira, L. C., & Almeida, C. B. (2015). Employee turnover and organizational performance: a study of the Brazilian retail sector. *Brazilian Business Review*, 12, (4), 27-56.
- Gibson, E.B. (2012). *Introduction to job satisfaction and employees' performance in the West Indies*. UK: Educational Inc.
- Glissmeyer, M. (2012). Role conflict, role ambiguity and intention to quit the organization: the case of law enforcement officers. *Journal of Management*, 26, (6), 1113-1131.
- Guest, D. E. (2004). Flexible employment contracts, psychological contracts, and employee outcomes. An analysis and review of the evidence. *International Journal of Management Review*, 5 /6, (1), 1-19.
- Gupta, M., Kumar, V., & Singh, M. (2014). Creating satisfied employees through workplace spirituality: a study of the private insurance sector in Punjab (India). *Journal of Business Ethics*, 122, (1), 79-88.
- Hair, J. F. Jr., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M. & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling, (2nd ed.)*. Canada: Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (2006). *Multivariate data analysis (6th Ed.)*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Mena, J. A. (2012). An Assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. *Journal of Academy of Marketing Sciences*, 40, 414-433.

- Igbal, A., Ijaz, M., Latif, F., & Mushtaq, H. (2015). Factors affecting the employees: a case study of the banking sector in Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 4, (8), 309-318.
- Intaraprasong, B., Dityen, W., Krugkrunjit, P., & Subhadrabandhu, T. (2012). Job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior of personnel at one university hospital in Thailand. *Journal of Medical Association Thailand*, 95, (6), 102-108.
- Ismail, A., Chandra Segaran, S.C., Cheekiong, T., & Ong, G. (2007). The mediating role of motivation to learn in the relationship between supervisors role and job performance. *The Sixth Asian Conference of the Academy of HRD, Dec 3-5, 2007, Beijing, China*. Beijing, China.
- Jacobs, E.J., & Roodt, G. (2011). The mediating effect of knowledge sharing between organisational culture and turnover intentions of professional nurses. *South African Journal of Information Management*, 13, (1), 1–6. DOI: 10.4102/sajim.v13i1.425.
- JCR-VIS SECTOR UPDATE. (2019). *Hotel Industry; demand for the sector is primarily dependent on the growth in the tourism sector*. UK: JCR-VIS Credit Rating Company Limited.
- Jones Lang LaSalle IP. (2019). *Hotel investment outlook*. achieve ambatiour. JLL Hotel and Hospitality.
- Kalidass, A., & Bahron, A. (2015). The relationship between perceived supervisor support, perceived organizational support, organizational commitment, and employee turnover intention. *International journal of business administration*, 6, (5), 85-89.
- Kang, H., Gatling, A. & Kim, J. (2014). The impact of supervisory support on organizational commitment, career satisfaction, and turnover intention for hospitality frontline employees. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism*, 14, (1), 1-12.
- Kartika, G., & Purba, D. (2018). Job satisfaction and turnover intention: The mediating effect of affective commitment. *Psychological Research on Urban Society*, 1, (2), 100-106.
- Khan, M. S., Khan, I., Kundi, G. M., Yar, N. B., & Saif, N. (2014). The impact of demography on intention to leave among the academicians in the public and private sectors universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Industrial Engineering Letters*, 4, (3), 1-10.
- Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2004). *Organizational behavior 5th ed*. New York: McGraw-Hill Inc.
- Lambert, E. G., & Hogan, N. (2009). The importance of job satisfaction and organizational commitment in shaping turnover intent. *Criminal Justice Review*, 34, 96–118.
- Latif, M.S., Ahmad, M., Qasim, M., Mushtaq, M., Ferdoos, A., & Naeem, H. (2013). Impact of employees' job satisfaction on organizational performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5, (5), 166-171.
- Lee, D., Hampton, M., & Jeyacheya, J. (2015). The political economy of precarious work in the tourism industry in small island developing states. *Review of International Political Economy*, 22, (1), 194-223. doi:10.1080/09692290.2014.887590.
- Lee, S. (2018). Employee turnover and organizational performance in U.S. Federal Agencies. *American Review of Public Administration*, 48, (6), 522–534.

- Lee, Y. D, Lain, J.W., & Chen, C.Y. (1999). A study on the measurement of productivity for the white-collar employees-A case of electronic industry in Taiwan. *The Chinese Military Academy Journal*, 14, 345-361.
- Li, Y., Sawhney, R., & Tortorella, G. L. (2019). Empirical analysis of factors impacting turnover intention among manufacturing workers. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 14, (4), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v14n4p1>.
- Mathis, C.L., Fredrick, G.Y., & Kenneth, O.P. (2009). One more time. how do you motivate employees? *Harvard Business Review*, 46, (1), 53-62.
- McKay, S., Jefferys, S., Paraksevopoulou, A., & Keles, J. (2012). *Study on precarious work and social rights*. Retrieved from https://www.google.nl/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwj0meeO8q_NAhUJPxQKHUbNCQ4QFggcMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fec.europa.eu%2Fsocial%2FblobServlet%3FdocId%3D7925%26langId%3Den&usg=AFQjCNH6_NtbzmiMqrH5xbFLyevMBSIFJQ.
- Meral, E., Irge, S., Aksoy, S., & Alpan, L. (2012). The impact of ethical leadership and leadership effectiveness on employees' turnover intention: the media work-related stress. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, (12), 289-200.
- Mohammed, I. (2016). Job satisfaction and employee performance: an empirical approach. *The Millennium University Journal*, 1, (1), 1-14.
- Mohapatra, B. K, & Srivastava, A. K. (2003). *A study of the relationship of perceived work environment with job attitude, performance, and health*. banaras: Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, Department of Psychology, Hindu University.
- Motowidlo, S.J., & Van Scotter, J.R. (1994). Evidence that task performance should be distinguished from contextual performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 79,(4), 475-48.
- Mugove, L. A., & Mukanzi, C. (2018). Determinants of employee's turnover in the selected public universities in Kenya. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 5, (4), 1098 - 1119.
- Ndulue, T. I., & Ekechukwu, H. C. (2016). Impact of job satisfaction on employees' performance: A study of Nigerian breweries plc, Kaduna. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5, (11), 1-23.
- Nmadu, G. (2013). Employees' performance and its effects on their job performance in the workplace. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5, (11), 13-23.
- Opkara, J. O. (2002). The impact of salary differential on managerial job satisfaction. a study of the gender gap and its implications for management education and practice in a developing economy. *Journal of Business for Developing Nation*, 65-92.
- Oxford Economics. (2018). *The economic impact of the US hotel industry*. oxford, England: American Hotel and Lodging Association Educational Foundation.
- Oxford Economics for the British Hospitality Association. (2018). *The economic contribution of the UK hospitality industry*. UK: British Hospitality Association.
- Öztürk, F. (2010). *Determinants of organizational citizenship behavior among knowledge workers: the role of job characteristics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment*. Ankara,

Turkey: Unpublished Graduate Thesis, Master-degree Program in Business Administration, Middle East Technical University.

- Perrin, O. (2016). *The difference between employees' performance and productivity*. Retrieved January 11th, 2019, from Employee Connect: <https://www.employeeconnect.com>.
- Platt, J., & Sobotka, L. (2010). *Psychological management of individual performance*. Wales: John Wiley & Sons.
- Pradhan, R. K., & Jana, L. K. (2016). Employees' performance at the workplace; conceptual model and empirical validation. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 5, (1), 1-17.
- PricewaterhouseCoopers. (2017). *African insights hotels outlook: 2017–2021*. Retrieved August 11, 2018, from www.pwc.co.za/hospitality-and-leisure.
- Pushpakumari, M. D. (2008). The impact of job satisfaction on job performance: an empirical analysis. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management*, 89-106.
- Ramirez, D. L. (2012). *Organizational communication satisfaction and job satisfaction within university food service*. Manhattan, Kansas, USA: Unpublished Graduate Thesis, Master-degree Program in International Hospitality Management, Kansas State University.
- Rana, S., & Singh, V. (2016a). Employee empowerment and job satisfaction: an empirical study in its industry. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 21, (10), Ver.12, 23-29.
- Rijamampianina, R. (2015). Employee turnover rate and organizational performance in South Africa. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 13, (4-1), 240-253.
- Robbins, O. (2005). The Micro-analysis of job satisfaction; comments on taber and alliger. *Journal of Organisational Behaviour*, 16, (2), 123-126.
- Robbins, S. P, Odendaal A, & Roodt, G. (2003). *Organizational behaviour (9th ed)*. Cape Town: Prentice-Hall International.
- Robbins, S. P. (2001). *Organizational behaviour concepts controversies and applications*. USA: Prentice Hall International Inc.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2009). *Organisational behaviour 13th ed*. London: Pearson Education International Limited.
- Sahin, F. (2011). The interaction of self-leadership and psychological climate on job performance. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5,(5), 1787-1794.
- Sangaran, G., & Jeetesh, K. (2015). The effects of job satisfaction towards employee turnover in the hotel industry: A case study of hotels in Kuala Lumpur. *Journal of tourism and hospitality*, 4, (1), 1-5.
- Schermerhorn, J., Hunt, J. G., & Osborn, R. N. (2001). *Organizational behaviour, 7th ed*. Asia: John Wiley & Sons.
- Schermerhorn, J., Hunt, J., & Osborn, R. (2005). *Organizational Behaviour (9th ed.)*. New York. NY: John Wiley.
- Silla, I., Gracia, F., & Peiro, J. M . (2005). Job insecurity and health-related outcomes among different types of temporary workers. *Economics of Industrial Democracy*, 26: 89–117.

- Singh, J. K., & Jain, M. (2013). A Study of employees' job satisfaction and its impact on their performance. *Journal of Indian Research*, 1, (4), 105-111.
- Smith, F.J., Kendall, Z.W., & Hulin, E.M. (2007). *Job satisfaction of professional and paraprofessional library staff at Chapel Hill North Carolina*. North Carolina: University of North Carolina.
- Smith-Randolph, D. (2005). Predicting the effect of extrinsic and intrinsic job satisfaction factors on recruitment and retention of rehabilitation professionals. *Journal of Health Care Management*, 50, (1), 49-61.
- Spector, P. (2008). *Industrial and organizational psychology*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.
- Spector, P. E., & Jex, S. M. (1998). Development of four self-report measures of job stressors and strain: interpersonal conflict at work scale, organizational constraints scale, quantitative workload inventory, and physical symptoms inventory. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 3, (4), 356.
- Sprigg, C. A., & Jackson, P. R. (2006). Call centers as lean service environments: job-related strain and the mediating role of work design. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 11, (2), 197-212. doi:10.1037/1076-8998.11.2.197.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Using multivariate statistics (5th ed.)*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Tai, W.T. (2006). Effects of training framing, general self-efficacy, and training motivation on trainee's training effectiveness. *Personal Review*, 35, (1), 51-65.
- Taye, D., & Gentnet, B. (2020). The impact of employees' turnover on organizational performance in Wada Walabu University, Ethiopia. *American Journal of Pure and Applied Biosciences*, 2, (3), 51-63.
- Tett, R. P., & Meyer, J. P. (1993). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment, turnover intention, and turnover: Path analyses based on meta-analytic findings. *Journal of Personnel Psychology*, 46, (2), 259-293. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1993.tb00874>.
- Tol, R. J. (2002). Estimates of the damage costs of climate change. part 1: benchmark estimates. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 21, (1), 47-73.
- Tsai, H., Yeung, S., & Yim, P.H. (2011). Hotel selection criteria used by mainland Chinese and foreign individual travelers to Hong Kong. *International Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Administration*, 12, (3), 252-267.
- Tsai, W.C & Tai, K. (2003). Perceived importance as a mediator of the relationship between training assignment and training motivation. *Personal Review*, 31, (2), 51-13.
- Viswesvaran, C., & Ones, D. S. (2000). Perspectives on models of job performance. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 8,(8), 216-226.
- Wistow, J., Blackman, T., Byrne, D., & Wistow, G. (2015). *Studying health inequalities: an applied approach*. Policy Press.
- Wu, H., Zhao, Y., Wang, J.N & Wang, L. (2010). Factors associated with occupational stress among Chinese doctors: a cross-sectional survey. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 83, (2), 155-164.

Yakoob, N. B. (2019). The mediating role of job satisfaction on leadership style and employees' turnover intention relationship. *Opcion, Año 35, N° Especial*, 19, (1), 2900-2924.